

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF STUDY CATEGORIES "ASTONISHMENT"

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Abstract: In recent decades, the human factor in language has become decisive in the linguistic scientific tradition. Increasingly, the attention of researchers is turning to the analysis of emotional phenomena from the point of view of the anthropological approach. "Astonishment" within the framework of this dissertation research is considered as an emotional pragmalinguistic category, which is objectified in speech situations presented in Uzbek and English fairy tale discourses. The dissertation work is devoted to a comparative analysis of the ways of objectifying the category "astonishment" in the emotive space of Uzbek and English fairy tale discourses from the position of pragmalinguistics

Keywords: "astonishment", "philosophical", motivation, relationships, Chainsmokers", "heavy smokers".

Аннотация: В последние десятилетия человеческий фактор в языке стал определяющим в лингвистической научной традиции. Все чаще внимание исследователей обращается к анализу эмоциональных явлений с точки зрения антропологического подхода. «Удивление» в рамках данного диссертационного исследования рассматривается как эмоциональная прагмалингвистическая категория, которая объективируется в речевых ситуациях, представленных в узбекском и английском сказочных дискурсах. Диссертационная работа посвящена сравнительному анализу способов объективации категории «удивление» в эмотивном пространстве узбекского и английского сказочных дискурсов с позиций прагмалингвистики.

Ключевые слова: «удивление», «философский», мотивация, отношения, заядлые курильщики, заядлые курильщики.

INTRODUCTION

The subject of the research is the features of the verbal objectification of the category "astonishment" in Uzbek and English fairy tale discourses from the point of view of functional and hidden pragmalinguistics.

The relevance of the study is due to the unrelenting interest of modern linguistic thought in the interaction between the author and the reader, in particular, in the field of the formation of certain emotional experiences. The least studied emotions from the standpoint of both latent and comparative pragmalinguistics include the emotion of astonishment, which plays an important role in the process of cognition. The emotion of astonishment is most clearly represented in the fairy tale discourse, as it accompanies the reader throughout the reading of the fairy tale, determining his emotional perception.

The study is based on the following hypothesis: the category "astonishment" is objectified in a speech situation and represents an interaction between the sender of the text, who chooses the illocutions "forcing to astonishment" and actualizes the hidden nuances of meaning, forming the recipient's attitude and violating his expectations, and the recipient, who identifies the situation of astonishment by certain linguistic means and techniques. The objectification of the category "astonishment" in Uzbek and English fairy tale discourses has both similarities and differences, determined by national and cultural characteristics.

The purpose of the dissertation research is to compare the ways of objectifying the category "astonishment" in speech situations in Uzbek and English fairy tale discourses in the pragmalinguistic aspect.

Achieving this goal involves solving the following tasks:

1. Conduct a comparative analysis of the objectification of the category of "astonishment" in the speech situation in Uzbek and English fairy tale discourses from the position of functional pragmalinguistics, namely:
 - to consider the choice of illocutions "forcing to astonishment" on the part of the sender of the text;

- identify possible ways to implement the category of "astonishment" in the speech of the recipient of the text.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

This section summarizes the historical experience of studying astonishment in philosophical, psychological and linguistic aspects.

In philosophy, "astonishment" is ranked among the most "philosophical" emotions, since it "is present and rules in every step of philosophy".

In antiquity, "astonishment" was seen as an intellectual feeling. Aristotle notes the connection between human intellectual activity and emotions. He comes to the conclusion that astonishment is a stimulus to knowledge.

I. Kant considers "astonishment" as an emotion and associates two modalities with it, namely, pleasure and displeasure that a person experiences in the process of thinking. At the same time, I. Kant, following R. Descartes, points out that the emotion of astonishment can turn into amazement. According to him, confusion from any unexpectedness is the excitement of feeling. At first, it delays the natural course of thought, and therefore it is felt by a person as an unpleasant experience. But afterwards, an unpleasant experience contributes to a rush of thoughts and makes this sensation pleasant. The highest degree of astonishment arises when the wondering person doubts the reality of what is happening, and the subject of astonishment depends on the person's past experience: lack of experience entails the frequent emergence of the emotion of astonishment in everyday situations.

At the very beginning of learning English, students usually do not suffer from a lack of motivation. But as soon as a deeper mastery of a foreign language begins, various difficulties appear in understanding the information provided, at this moment the level of motivation may fall. Here the teacher should pay attention to the tools that he has available to motivate the student. The student's love for the subject is related to how interesting and emotional the teacher conducts classes. Astonishment helps to form the interest and motivation of the student.

Astonishment is a sign of an indifferent attitude to information.

The pedagogy of astonishment is the pedagogy of relationships, not demands, since the teacher creates a field of relationships for further joint cognitive activity. The pedagogy of astonishment is based on the principle of taking into account interests, life situation, characteristics and level of development, as well as activity and freedom of creativity. The pedagogy of astonishment continues the humanistic trend, where the main thing is the personality as an object of education and training.

Basic elements of astonishment pedagogy:

Astonishment with a fact. This leads to a desire to learn more about this information and further motivation to independently search for interesting facts. With regard to a foreign language, you can draw students' attention to the peculiarities of vocabulary, grammar, culture, traditions. Explain to them that they have a certain meaning that can be applied in a broader sense. For example, not all students know about left-hand traffic in England, and the well-known group "Chainsmokers" is translated into Uzbek as "heavy smokers".

This is how the teacher presents information, possession of tools. An extraordinary presentation of even elementary information can be surprising. Games in English lessons, even with the senior level, bear fruit immediately - students quickly become involved in the game, experiencing sincere astonishment.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

The character belongs to the category of the main meaningful universals of the text. The character's emotions are portrayed as a special psychic reality. The totality of emotions in the text is a kind of dynamic set that changes as the plot develops, reflecting the inner world of the character in various circumstances, in relations with other characters.

Extracting emotive vocabulary from the text and considering it in isolation from the text gives only an approximate, most superficial idea of the set of emotive meanings that are realized in the text as a whole in terms of their uniformity/diversity, monotonicity/polytonality. So, for example, in V. M. Shukshin's story "Resentment", the image of negative emotive meanings prevails, the tone of which is set by the title. Similar texts gravitating toward monotony include his stories "Grief", "Vanka Teplyashin" (the dominant series is "longing"), "Accident in a restaurant" (the dominant series is "love, sympathy"), "Medic Volodya" (dominant "joy"), "Zero-zero whole" (dominant "anger, indignation"). At the same time, the manner of psychological analysis of V. M. Shukshin is distinguished by the image of polytonality, the variety of embodied emotive meanings. So, in the story "I Believe!" a bright palette of emotional meanings is presented (pity, anger, love, hatred, excitement, peace, astonishment, etc.), the extreme poles of which are feelings of faith and longing.

Emotive meanings have a different rank of significance in the text, which is revealed by the analysis of their structural and syntactic embodiment, i.e. analysis of the use of emotive vocabulary in various contextual conditions. The condition for the existence of general textual emotive meanings is a holistic text. The conductor of these meanings is primarily emotive vocabulary. Phrasal and fragmentary emotive meanings are also created by emotive vocabulary.

The main methods of textual promotion of the most important elements of the content of the text are the repetition of the meaning and means denoting it, on the one hand, and the use of means of occasional nomination, on the other.

Of particular importance in the generation of key textual emotive meanings are words that reveal the diversity and richness of lexical connections in the text.

In V. M. Shukshin's story "The Sufferings of Young Vaganov", the emotive meaning "suffering", which characterizes the psychology of the main character, has a key aesthetic significance. This meaning is placed in a strong position of the text - in the title, which focuses the reader's attention on it, focuses on the perception of the emotive content of a certain tone. The entire subsequent text of the story is an artistic-figurative concretization of the emotive semantics of the title.

CONCLUSION

The emotionality of the text is fed by all emotive meanings: explicit and implicit, dictal and modal, expressed in the text, therefore it depends on the entire content of the text as a whole and, above all, on its emotive content. Realizing this dependence and conditionality of its holistic content of the text, it is necessary to take into account the inequality of various factors of its generation.

An essential feature of the text is its multicomponent nature, polyphony. Polyphonism of emotional tones arises as a result of the interaction between the level of the author's image and the level of characters' images. But for all the complexity of the emotive content of the text, there is usually an orientation towards the actualization of a certain emotional component, which becomes dominant and is perceived as the personification of the emotional tone of the entire text as a whole (cf. cheerful, sad, gloomy, lyrical, optimistic, sad and other definitions-epithets to works of art). The harmonic unity of tonality holds the text together and determines its semantic integrity.

Of course, the emotional tone absorbs all the emotive meanings contained in the text, but the leading part in the choir of textual emotions still belongs to the **intentional emotive meanings** that reflect the author's position and concept. Of particular importance is the place of emotive vocabulary in the syntagmatics of the text, for example, the use of emotive vocabulary in **the title position**. This is due to

the fact that the title contains in a compressed, compressed form the information of the text, reflects the semantic determinant of the structure. The title, according to Umberto Eco, is “the key to interpretation ... Perception is given by it” (Eco. Notes on the margins of the Name of the Rose, 1988, p. 89). If emotive vocabulary is in this position, it charges the entire text with its tone. So, V. M. Shukshin actively uses emotive vocabulary in the function of titles, interpreting in a certain emotional sense the events depicted in the text: “The suffering of young Vaganov”, “Woe”, “Resentment”, “I believe!”, “Persistent”, “Freak” and others.

The emotional tonality of the text is also created by the repeated repetition of a separate stylistic device, so any **repetition** is not only a means of textual communication, but also a prerequisite for the emergence of emotional tonality, and repeated lexical nomination is its strong and effective means, especially if the vocabulary of emotions is duplicated. Usually what is indicated in repetition is the center, the subject of writer's aspirations.

It is necessary to distinguish between phrasal and textual emotional tones. They differ both externally - according to the specific conditions of implementation, and internally - in terms of functional and semantic orientation. **Phrasal emotional tonality** is the foundation, the basis that helps to comprehend and perceive **textual** emotional tonality, which usually includes phrasal and relies on it.

In the sphere of the text, the author's super-evaluation dominates, fastening all the semantic components of the text, including emotive meanings, and ensuring the integrity of the content of the text.

As you can see, a literary text reveals a variety of emotive meanings that differ in content, degree of concretization, compositional conditions for their expression, in function in the text and in correlation with the subject of emotions experiencing them (dictal-character, modal-author's). Emotive textual meanings interact with each other in various ways: they intersect and diverge, attract and repel. As a result

of such interaction, the emotive content of a literary text is formed, the categorical basis of which is the emotional tone of the text

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